

STUDY ON OFF-AXIAL AND CYCLIC TENSILE PROPERTIES OF FEVE REINFORCED MEMBRANES

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ABSTRACT

Fabric reinforced membranes are widely used as tensioned structure material for architectural membrane structure which are usually considered to be anisotropic. In different directions, fabric reinforced membrane materials exhibit different mechanical behaviours, such as fracture strength, elongation, fracture morphology, stiffness, etc. Besides, the membrane structure is often subjected to wind loads because of the long-term exposure to the air, which can be simplified as cyclic loading on it. Cyclic loading action reduces the normal tension state of the membrane material in use and increases the instability of the whole structure which may cause irreparable damage to the material. In this study, a low-temperature curing flexible composite material was firstly fabricated by using Fluoroethylene Vinyl Ether (FEVE) resin. Then the off-axial tensile and cyclic load properties of FEVE/polyester reinforced membrane were investigated which show typical nonlinearity, non-elasticity and anisotropy. Additionally, several classical failure criterions were used to predict bias tensile strength which found that Tsai-Hill criterion and Norris criterion could make a good prediction in most case except that in small off-axial angles while Yeh-Stratton criterion could give more reasonable results at small bias angle. These results are expected to provide guidance for practical applications of membrane structure materials, structural cutting and the selection of pre-tension.

1 INTRODUCTION

Membrane structural material for building is a kind of flexible composite material, which is generally obtained by fiber aggregation as reinforcement and functional resin as matrix. Among them, the reinforcement provides the required mechanical properties of the membrane material, while the matrix provides excellent self-cleaning property, weather resistance, and protects the bearing layer from the direct influence of humidity, acidity and alkalinity in the environment.^[1,2]

Fabric reinforced membranes are usually used as tensioned structure material for architectural membrane structure, and they are considered to be anisotropic. Fabric reinforced membranes have different strength, elongation, breaking form, stiffness and so on in different directions which has aroused the interest of many researchers.^[3-6] In addition, due to the long-term exposure to the air, the membrane structure often withstands the effect of wind force, which can be simplified as cyclic loading on it. Cyclic loading action reduces the normal tension state of the membrane material in use and increases the instability of the whole structure. So it is also necessary to investigate cyclic tensile properties and mechanical models under on-axial, off-axial, uniaxial and biaxial cyclic loading.^[7-10]

In this paper, a low temperature forming Fluoroethylene Vinyl Ether (FEVE)/polyester membrane was first developed. Then the uniaxial tensile properties of FEVE/polyester reinforced membrane were tested, and its off-axial tensile properties in seven directions were also tested and analysed. Besides, the failure strengths of different bias angles were predicted with several strength criterions. Finally combining with the actual application by wind force, the cyclic load action was applied to FEVE/polyester reinforced membrane, and the strength, modulus and elongation of the membrane material under cyclic stress were investigated. These results can provide some basis for the practical use of membrane structure materials, structural cutting and the selection of pre-tension.

2 EXPERIMENTS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials and preparation

FEVE/polyester reinforced membrane was prepared by impregnation and coating several times and then drying. The optimum curing temperature was 160 °C, curing temperature was 4 min, and the number of coating layers was 3. The parameters and properties of the prepared FEVE/polyester reinforced membrane were listed in Table 1.

Specimen	Fabric density / picks·cm ⁻¹	Area density / g·m ⁻²	Break strength in warp / N·2.5cm ⁻¹	Break strength in weft / N·2.5cm ⁻¹
FEVE/polyester membrane	9×9	372	1640	1278

Table 1: Parameters and performance of FEVE/polyester reinforced membrane.

2.2 Test Method

The uniaxial tensile, off-axial tensile and cyclic load properties of FEVE/polyester reinforced membrane were investigated according to ASTM D4851. The specimen for bias tensile test were prepared to be a strip by cutting the samples with off-axial angles of 0°, 15°, 30°, 45°, 60°, 75°, and 90° from warp direction. The effective length, clamped length and specimen's width were 75mm, 50mm and 25mm, respectively. The loading rate was 50mm/min and there were 5 specimens for each case. The test equipment was CMT 5204 micro-controlled electronic multi-function testing machine and the test was carried out at room temperature of 20 °C and in the relative humidity of 65 % RH.

As for the uniaxial cyclic test, the specimen specification was consistent with that of uniaxial on-axial tensile test. For the experimental protocols, the rate of loading-unloading and stress amplitude are two important parameters. In this paper, the speeds of loading and unloading with the rate of 1 kN/min were the same and the stress amplitudes for warp and weft samples were 0-328 N/2.5cm and 0-255 N/2.5cm, where 328 N/2.5cm and 255 N/2.5cm were one fifth of the warp and weft tensile strength, respectively. Additionally, the times of loading-unloading cycles was 15 and each group was tested with 3 specimens. After cyclic loading, mono-uniaxial tests were carried out on the cyclic samples to investigate mechanical behaviors of FEVE/polyester reinforced membrane after cyclic loading. The test protocol was identical to that of uniaxial tensile test and carried out to obtain failure stress, failure strain and elastic modulus.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Off-axial Tensile Properties

The tension curves of FEVE/polyester reinforced membrane on-axial and off-axial tensile tests were plot in Fig. 1. As shown in the results, the tensile properties of this membrane are obviously nonlinear and quasi-orthotropic which could be attributed to the addition of resin matrix, the typical plain woven structure of reinforced fabrics and the interaction between coating matrix and reinforced fabrics. From Fig. 1, it can be seen that the tension curves are nonlinear and can be divided into three typical parts including initial linear tension stage, nonlinear tension transition stage and linear tensile strengthen stage. When the external load was applied to the samples of on-axial (0° and 90°) tension tests, the coating and reinforced fabrics were stretched simultaneously in the first stage. Then the longitudinal yarns attempted to straighten and at the same time slip occurred at the interface between reinforcements and matrix during the nonlinear stage. In the final stage, the straightened fabrics together with the resin coating endured the external loading which exhibited linear features in the tension curves once more. Nevertheless, there are some differences in those tensile behaviours of off-axial specimens. First, the bearing yarns of off-axial samples attempted to rotate to parallel to the vertical line after the initial linear tension which caused the appearance of nonlinear region in advance.

Second, owing to the deformation caused by rotation and straighten of longitudinal yarns was larger than that of pure straighten, the nonlinear regions of off-axial samples are wider than those of on-axial samples. Furthermore, with the bias angle increasing, the deformation caused by yarns rotation and interaction between resin and rotating yarns increase also. Hence, it can be seen from Fig. 1 that the nonlinear regions of off-axial tension with bigger bias angles become wider and the third linear strengthen stages come later.

Figure 1: FEVE membrane off-axial tension curves in seven directions.

Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 show more intuitive statistical results of the tensile strength and the strain at break from which we can see that the uniaxial tensile strength decreases and the corresponding breaking strain increases with the bias angle increases. As is shown in Fig. 2, the tensile strengths of fiber directions are obviously larger compared to those of bias directions. However, it is worth noting that the warp strength is higher than the weft strength although the yarn densities in warp and weft are equal and in theory the warp strength is more easily lost during the weaving procedure. This phenomenon may be ascribed to the coating process. In general, the warp direction of fabric is in tensional state during coating process and, meanwhile, the weft yarns are becoming more crimped which may explain the greater elongation of weft direction than the warp. Thanks to the warp tension, warp yarns are stretching to parallel to each other and then this state is fixed by the coating matrix. As a consequence, the warp tension strength is enhanced. For the off-axial tensile test, there are three failure modes existing in the failure samples, including pure tensile failure, pure shear failure and mixed failure combined tensile and shear. Among them, pure tensile failure takes place at the angle of 0° and 90° where the main bearing elements are the strength of yarns parallel to the load direction and when the bias angle is near 45°, the pure shear failure happens where the bearing elements are interfacial bonding and friction of resin and fibers. As for the other angles, it is always mixed failure of tensile and shear where yarns bearing, interfacial bonding and friction existing simultaneously.

Figure 2: Polar coordinate diagrams of off-axial tension.

Although from the global aspect the tensile strength is decreasing with the increasing of bias angle, it is supposed to be noticed that there is a sudden decrease in the range of small bias angle such as 0°-15° and 75°-90°, as is shown in Fig. 2. However, in Fig. 3, unlike the tensile strength, the corresponding elongation does not decrease so quickly. This phenomenon can be attributed to the cutoff yarns of the off-axial samples. Due to the unique structure of woven plain fabric and the specimen specification, the number of cutoff yarns is very sensitive to the bias angle. Only in very small angles (smaller than $\arctan 25/75$, near 18°) are there some complete yarns existing in the strip samples. Despite this, the tensile strength still decreases very severely with the bearing yarns reduce drastically. In this range of bias angle, the bearing components include tensile strength and shear force. Nevertheless, with the bias angle further increasing, only cutoff yarns exist in the samples. So, the tensile strengths at the angles between 15° and 75° have not shown big difference. For the samples at the angles 18°-72°, there are only shear strengths in the tensioned specimens. The difference between them is that with the bias angle increasing, the length of the principal bearing yarns embedded in the coating becomes smaller. Smaller the length, easier are the yarns pulled out which may induce earlier failure of samples. When the length is big enough, the interaction including adhesion and friction between coating and yarn is more dominant than yarn's tensile strength, which lead to mixed failure of tensile and shear. Also, the more biased the bearing yarns are, the smaller the vertical component force of yarns' tensile stress is. Likewise, as discussed above, the more biased the bearing yarns are, the greater the deformation caused by yarns rotation is. So, from the analysis above, it can be concluded that FEVE/polyester reinforced membrane is typically anisotropic in tensile properties which is worthy of attention in the form-finding analysis and the cutting pattern design.

Figure 3: Polar coordinate diagrams of elongation under off-axial tension.

3.2 Failure Strength Criterion for FEVE/Polyester Reinforced Membrane

A strength criterion with operationally simple expressions and high prediction accuracy for flexible composites can play an important role in actual engineering design. Hitherto, a lot of strength criteria have been proposed such as Tsai-Hill criterion, Yeh-Stratton criterion, Norris criterion, Hasin criterion, some novel modified criteria or biaxial failure criteria and so on.^[3-5, 11-15] Here, taking account into convenient use and prediction precision, several classical failure criteria are chosen to predict off-axial tensile strength of FEVE/polyester reinforced membrane, which are as follows

Tsai-Hill criterion

$$\frac{\sigma_x^2}{X^2} + \frac{\sigma_y^2}{Y^2} - \frac{\sigma_x \sigma_y}{X^2} + \frac{\tau_{xy}^2}{S^2} = 1 \quad (1)$$

Norris criterion

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_x}{X}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_y}{Y}\right)^2 + \frac{\tau_{xy}^2}{S^2} - \frac{\sigma_x \sigma_y}{XY} = 1 \quad (2)$$

Hasin criterion

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_x}{X}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{xy}}{S}\right)^2 = 1 \quad (3)$$

Yeh-Stratton criterion

$$\frac{\sigma_x}{X} + \frac{\sigma_y}{Y} - \frac{\sigma_x \sigma_y}{X^2} + \frac{\tau_{xy}^2}{S^2} = 1 \quad (4)$$

where σ_x and σ_y are the normal stress in the longitudinal and transverse direction, τ_{xy} is the shear stress, X , Y are the longitudinal tensile strength, the transverse tensile strength and S is the shear strength.

For the off-axis specimens that suffer an applied stress σ_θ at angle θ to the principal direction x , the principal directions' stresses can be obtained as below^[12,15]:

$$\sigma_x = \sigma_\theta \cos^2 \theta \quad (5)$$

$$\sigma_y = \sigma_\theta \sin^2 \theta \quad (6)$$

$$\tau_{xy} = -\sigma_\theta \sin \theta \cos \theta \quad (7)$$

Substitute equations (5), (6), and (7) into equations (1), (2), (3), and (4), the Tsai-Hill criterion, Norris criterion, Hasin criterion, and Yeh-Stratton criterion can be formulated as follows:

Tsai-Hill criterion

$$\frac{\cos^4 \theta}{X^2} + \left(\frac{1}{S^2} - \frac{1}{X^2}\right) \sin^2 \theta \cos^2 \theta + \frac{\sin^4 \theta}{Y^2} = \frac{1}{\sigma_\theta^2} \quad (8)$$

Norris criterion

$$\frac{\cos^4 \theta}{X^2} + \left(\frac{1}{S^2} - \frac{1}{XY}\right) \sin^2 \theta \cos^2 \theta + \frac{\sin^4 \theta}{Y^2} = \frac{1}{\sigma_\theta^2} \quad (9)$$

Hasin criterion

$$\frac{\cos^4 \theta}{X^2} + \frac{\sin^2 \theta \cos^2 \theta}{S^2} = \frac{1}{\sigma_\theta^2} \quad (10)$$

Yeh-Stratton criterion

$$\frac{\sigma_\theta \cos^2 \theta}{X^2} + \left(\frac{1}{S^2} - \frac{1}{X^2}\right) \sigma_\theta^2 \sin^2 \theta \cos^2 \theta + \frac{\sigma_\theta \sin^2 \theta}{Y^2} = 1 \quad (11)$$

Among these parameters, X , Y can be got from uniaxial tensile test results, and by picture-frame method the shear strength S is obtained^[6,16]

$$S = \frac{P}{\sqrt{2}l_0} \quad (12)$$

where P is the applied load in picture-frame test and l_0 is the length of picture-frame's arm. Besides, P can be got by using the following formula

$$P = k \cdot \sin \alpha \cdot X_{45} \cdot l_0 \quad (13)$$

where X_{45} is the uniaxial tensile strength at bias angle 45° , k is the converting efficiency between P and X_{45} whose magnitude is between 0.7 and 0.8, α ranging from 85° and 95° is the angle between warp and weft yarns^[6] and substitute equation (13) into equation (12), l_0 is eliminated. Thus, σ_θ at bias angle θ can be calculated with X , Y and X_{45} . That is to say, the permissible stress at any bias angle can be predicted by the bias tensile results of 0° , 45° and 90° .

Figure 4 shows the predicted results of different strength criterions and experimental data. Results show that Tsai-Hill criterion, Norris criterion, and Yeh-Stratton criterion can predict off-axial tensile stress well on the whole while Hasin criterion is not suitable to be adopted when the bias angle is close to the transverse direction. Among them, Tsai-Hill criterion and Norris criterion can make a good prediction in most case except that in small off-axial angles while Yeh-Stratton criterion can give more reasonable results at small bias angle. Certainly, there are slight deviations existing in the prediction of

these failure strength criterion which could be improved by considering the interaction between longitudinal and transverse normal stress, and the interaction between normal stress and shear stress.

Figure 4: Failure strength prediction of different strength criterions.

3.3 Cyclic Tensile Properties

Fig. 5 shows the representative cyclic curve of FEVE/polyester membrane in which the membrane behaves obviously nonelastic properties and shows typical ratcheting effect. As shown in the results, with the cycle times increase, the elastic modulus and the residual strain increase. In the cyclic curves, the loading and unloading curves do not coincide and even form hysteresis rings with each other which can be mainly ascribed to the viscosity and energy dissipations. Besides, the warp strength decreased after cyclic loading which may be attributed to damage accumulation of material. Nevertheless, the weft strength after cyclic loading didn't change. Maybe, the residual strain can reflect the damage accumulation to a certain degree. As shown in Fig. 6, the weft residual strain is lower than that of the warp.

Figure 5: FEVE membrane Tensile curve under cyclic loading.

In Fig. 5, the secant slope of cyclic curve which can be used to calculate the elastic modulus is growing gradually with the cycle times growing. Meanwhile, the residual strain is also accumulating and significant strain hardening phenomenon appears at last. There is a more intuitive comparison in Fig. 6, in the initial stage, the sample are easier to tensile resulting in bigger residual strain increments and more significant nonlinearity. From the global aspect, the residual strain is increasing constantly with the cycle times increase. However, it is a noteworthy phenomenon that the residual strain

increment is decreasing at the same time. And when the cycle times comes to 8, the residual strain tends to be identical and cyclic loading curve is significantly linear. During the loading process, there are three kinds of deformation including elastic deformation, recoverable viscous deformation and plastic deformation. The residual deformation in Fig. 6 is composed of recoverable viscous deformation and plastic deformation. Among them, plastic deformation is the critical factor of material failure in practical application.

Figure 6: Relation between residual deformation and cycle times.

During the service process, the membrane structure material always suffers cyclic load such as wind-induced load. As a viscoelasticity material, the deformation of membrane structure includes rotation, straightening and slippage of polymer chains in fibers and resin. Moreover, the primary valence bond and the secondary valence bond play important roles in the membrane deformation. When the external force is applied to the membrane, the primary valence bond and the secondary valence elongate and also the secondary valence ruptures. Then, some new secondary valence form at the new location. When the load is removed, some secondary valence come back to the original position while the other stay at the new location, which causes the formation of plastic deformation. Additionally, the resistance such as friction and adhesion existing in yarns, fibers, polymer chains and interface of fiber and resin contributes to plastic deformation, too.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The uniaxial tensile, off-axial tensile and cyclic load properties of FEVE/polyester reinforced membrane were investigated. The results show that this membrane structure material is typically nonlinear, nonelastic and anisotropic. To predict the off-axial tensile strength of FEVE/polyester reinforced membrane, several classical failure criterions were adopted. It was found that Tsai-Hill criterion and Norris criterion could make a good prediction in most case except that in small off-axial angles while Yeh-Stratton criterion could give more reasonable results at small bias angle. Then, uniaxial cyclic test was conducted on the membrane material. The results show that the increase of residual strain decreases as the times of cyclic loading increases, and the linearity of cyclic loading curve increases. The tensile linearity of the membrane increased after cyclic loading, but the strength decreased.

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